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Revisiting Rabindranath Tagore through the Lens of Google Scholar: a Unique Approach

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Google Scholar can search for publications from any source that Google, the world's largest search engine, can find. Furthermore, there are no restrictions on the languages that GS indexes. Regardless of the sources, GS covers all the channels that it can find.

Purpose: The present study attempts to explore the indexing policy and coverage of Google Scholar in terms of the inclusion of Rabindranath Tagore's literature. It also unsheathes the productivity portrait of Rabindranath Tagore, the Nobel laureate in literature.

Research problem: Earlier, no study was undertaken to highlight Tagore's visibility in Google Scholar (GS). The unavailability of the GS profile cannot portray the bibliometric image of Tagore.

Objectives: A complete scenario of Tagore's literature indexed by Google Scholar will be manifested and evaluated here in terms of citation metrics. The over-inclusive nature of the Google Scholar indexing policy will also be highlighted here.

Methodology: During this research, a verified GS profile was designed for the first time to manifest Tagore's presence with his writings under the GS database.

Findings: Accumulated data congregated from Tagore's GS profile reveals that the poet possesses 6246 citations. The indexes (h, g, i10) reveal the vogue of Tagore by displaying high numeric values. The top five cited novels also have visibility in this study. A year-wise citation graph of the author's GS profile is demonstrated in the latter part. Tagore's citation per paper value is 12.45. The unyielding popularity of Tagore's literature makes the citation graph continuously rise.

KEYWORDS:

Rabindranath Tagore; Citation Matrix; Vogue of Tagore

Introduction

Figure: 1- The Nobel Prize Medal Photo: Alexander Mahmoud; source: <https://www.nobelprize.org/>

On 27 November 1895, Alfred Nobel signed his last will, giving the largest share of his fortune to a series of prizes, the Nobel Prizes. Nobel Prize considers only the fields of literature, physics, chemistry, Physiology or Medicine, Economics, and peace for honouring Nobel. Glittering personalities of the fields that have a strong presence in any pioneer & outstanding 'works' for the betterment of mankind are being selected for getting this highest honour. Alfred Nobel benchmarked predefined criteria for getting this prize in the earlier mentioned seven fields. Whereas in the case of Nobel in Peace 'work' signifies any "peaceful instance means the person who shall have done the most or the best work for fraternity between nations, the abolition or reduction of standing armies and for the holding and promotion of peace congresses." (Excerpt from the will of Alfred Nobel). However, Literature laureates were defined in Nobel's will as "the person who shall have produced in the field of literature the most outstanding work in an ideal direction" (Facts on the Nobel Prize (2020)). The other five fields also have guidelines for getting a Nobel. The essence of the guidelines considers those works for Nobel which is 'pioneer invention' or those have 'outstanding literal value'. This study has a focal point that concentrates on a Nobel Laureate, who belongs to the field of Literature meanwhile; the will's note demonstrated about the Literature laureate was described.

The study focuses on Rabindranath Tagore, a renowned Nobel Laureate who belongs to the field of literature. However, he was a pioneer Noble laureate of India who glorified our country in 1913. Tagore became the first Non-European Nobel laureate of literature who established his presence in the world of Nobel laureates by qualifying the will of Alfred Nobel for Nobel in literature - "author who shall have produced in the field of literature the most outstanding work in an ideal direction ..." (Excerpt from the will of Alfred Nobel). To make this study feasible the pivotal point of the research is

concentrated towards the available literature on Tagore under the Google Scholar database.

Facts on the Nobel Prize in Literature, (2015) website highlighted that between 1901 and 2020, 117 Nobel laureates have been awarded around the world. The fact is that not all of these 120 years have had literature chosen for the Nobel Prize. In literature, there were 16 female laureates and 101 male laureates in only 113 years. In the years 1914, 1918, 1935, 1940, 1941, 1942, and 1943, no Nobel Prize in Literature was awarded. "If none of the works under consideration is determined to be of the importance indicated in the first paragraph, the award money will be reserved until the following year," according to the Nobel Foundation. If the reward cannot be given even then, the money will be put to the Foundation's restricted funds." There were fewer Nobel Prizes granted during World Wars I and II. (Facts on the Nobel Prize)

A Nobel laureate is dignified mostly for his or her one novel 'work' but passes over that various valuable 'works' also accomplished by them that are unturned. This research will contemplate all the 'untuned literature' with 'Nobel work' available under Google Scholar (GS) database.

In the broader sense, the universe of the subject is divided into science & technology, social science, and humanities. Digital Humanities make a bridge between technology and humanities. This research also tries to make a bridge by making archives using Google Scholar (GS) database. Here archiving attribute of the Google Scholar (GS) database is going to evaluate by making Rabindranath Tagore's GS profile by agglomerating Tagore's works of literature that are scattered all over the GS database. After selecting one by one document an archive for a particular author (e.g. Rabindranath Tagore) will be made. By creating that GS profile a scenario of citation and Indexes (h, g, I 10.) of Tagore will be documented and analyzed.

Rabindranath Tagore

Rabindranath Tagore was born in Calcutta. Tagore began to write verses at an early age. In the late 1870s from England, he completed his study. After returning to India he published several books of poetry starting in the 1880s. In 1901, Tagore initiated an experimental school in Shantiniketan where he agglomerated the best of Indian and Western traditions.

Rabindranath Tagore's writing is enormously populated in both Indian and Western learning traditions. Apart from fiction in the world of poetry, songs, stories, and dramas he manifested his own appearance. His literature also includes portrayals of common people's lives, literary criticism, philosophy, and social issues. Tagore's writings were in Bengali but later reached a broad audience all over the world after recasting his poetry in different languages. In contrast to the frenzied life in the West, his melancholy poetry was felt to convey the peace of the soul in harmony with nature.

Figure: 2-Photo from the Nobel Foundation archive

Tagore has a prominent footprint in the area of songs. Nowadays also his 2230 songs are consistently popular among Bengali-speaking people who generally belong from Bangladesh & the states of eastern India (Eg. West Bengal, Assam). The popular name in usage is Rabindrasangit, which refers to Tagore's songs. His songs certainly reflect Indian culture. He is supposed to be the only laureate who wrote the national anthem for two countries those are AmarShonarBangla, the national anthem of Bangladesh and the national anthem of India Jana GanaMana.

As a poet, Tagore's work was not confined to poems; he also created a strong presence in a variety of literary forms. Manasi (1890) [The Ideal One], Sonar Tari (1894) [The Golden Boat], Gitanjali (1910) [Song Offerings], Gitimalya (1914) [Wreath of Songs], and Balaka (1916) [The Flight of Cranes] are only a few of his notable works. The Gardener

(1913), Fruit-Gathering (1916), and The Fugitive (1921) are among the English translations of his poetry that do not always correspond to specific volumes in the Bengali original; and, despite its title, Gitanjali: Song Offerings (1912), the most acclaimed of them, contains poems from other works besides its namesake. Raja (1910) [The King of the Dark Chamber], Dakghar (1912) [The Post Office], Achalayatan (1912) [The Immovable], Muktaghara (1922) [The Waterfall], and Raktakaravi (1926) [Red Oleanders] are some of Tagore's most well-known dramas. Gora (1910), Ghare-Baire (1916) [The Home and the World], and Yogayog (1929) [Crosscurrents] are just a few of his short story collections and novels. He also composed music and dance dramas, articles of various kinds, trip diaries, and two memoirs, one in his middle years and the other soon before he died in 1941. Tagore also left a large number of sketches and paintings, as well as songs for which he composed the music.

Rabindranath Tagore also had his presence in politics. He was in support of the Indian nationalists for Freedom movement. Furthermore, Tagore travelled, lectured, and read his poetry extensively in Europe, the Americas, and East Asia and became a spokesperson for Indian independence from British colonial rule. His work Manifests his political views. He also wrote many patriotic songs that are evergreen. There was great love among the masses for such works. Tagore escalated the motivation for Indian independence.

Tagore renounced his knighthood, which was particularly notable. In addition, he did so in protest of the 1919 JallianwalaBagh massacre.

Finally, Rabindranath Tagore was a patriotic Indian. He was unquestionably a multi-talented individual. His contributions to literature, the arts, music, and politics have all been outstanding.

Review of Literature

The reason behind choosing Rabindranath Tagore

Ray, (2012) apprised Rabindranath Tagore, the multi-talented poet, and writer, who wrote his first poem at the age of eight, and by the time he died at the age of eighty, he had created literature in all forms, including poetry, short stories, novels, and essays; he had founded and edited various journals; he had written thousands of letters, and he had created over two thousand paintings (Ray(2012))

Figure:3-When Gandhi met the literature laureate, Rabindranath Tagore, in the year 1940. (Source: <https://www.nobelprize.org/>)

Ray & Sen, (2012) also added Rabindranath, the writer of two national anthems, has composed more than two thousand songs.

Ray & Sen, (2015) highlighted Tagore, India's Nobel Laureate poet, who was praised for his prolific publishing output. Between 1878 and 1941, he published 199 Bengali books, with 36 titles being published posthumously, for a total of 235 Bengali publications. When he entered the world of painting in his seventies (the last decade of his life), his literary output unexpectedly rose rather than decreased. In addition to generating almost 2000 paintings, he wrote 55 books. Tagore's output included poems, dramas, letters, novels, essays, ballads, travelogues, comedies, short tales, addresses, textbooks, and autobiographies, among other genres. His Bengali book productivity coefficient is 0.84, indicating that he had a consistent publication record throughout his literary career. He has published 91 of his 95 short stories on 16 different platforms. Short tales have a publishing density of 5.69, a publication concentration of 12.5, and a productivity coefficient of 0.32." (Albion (2012))

Previously, several scientometrics research projects on the works of Nobel Laureate scientists (Kademani, Kalyane and Kademani, (1996); Kademani, Kalyane and Jange. (1999); Gupta (1999); Kademani, Kalyane and Kademani (1994)) had been completed. Other investigations have been reported into the works of other prominent scientists (Hazarika, Sarma and Sen (2010); Kademani and Kalyane (1996); Kademani, Kalyane, Balakrishnan (1994); Kademani, Kalyane and Kademani (1996);) to create a scientometric portrait of them. However, Nobel Laureate Rabindranath Tagore's scientometrics analysis was not completed sooner.

The reason behind choosing Google Scholar

Harzing AW, and Alakangas S. (2016) observed Google scholar has been used successfully by individual researchers to track their scholarly output and citation and is thought to be as good as many other search engines as a source of bibliometric data. Thoma, B., & Chan, T. M. (2019) identified the case of SCOPUS (Elsevier) and Web of Science cost money to access and don't make their results publicly available but GS is open access so anyone can use it without paying fees. Further, while SCOPUS and

Web of Science can track and merge the publication metrics of individual faculty, they have more difficulty tracking more ambiguous research groups. Research Gate provides a free service that can be used by research or project groups; however, its citation tracking is incomplete because it is limited to the papers that have been uploaded to Research Gate. (Citations ResearchGate(2019). But GS is out of all types of problems faced by SCOPUS, Web of Science, and Research Gate.

Martin-Martin, A. et al. (2020) presented findings after Considering the most famous citation data sources like Microsoft Academic, Dimensions, OpenCitations Index (COCI), Web of Science (WoS), Scopus, and Google Scholar a differentiation in the citation was made which reflects Google Scholar found 88% of all citations, many of which were not found by the other sources, and nearly all citations found by the remaining sources (89–94%). Birkle et al. (2020) highlighted that in terms of record coverage, WoS covers more than 75 million records in its Core Collection (which includes its main citation indexes) and up to 155 million records when other regional and subject-specific citation indexes are included. Baas et al. (2020) showed up that Scopus claims to have access to over 76 million records. Van Noorden (2014) identified Google Scholar does not disclose official coverage figures, Delgado López-Cózar et al. (2019) & Gusebauer (2018) spotlighted recent independent studies estimated that shows GS covers well over 300 million records.

Harzing (2019) used her publication and citation record, as well as that of six top journals in Business & Economics, to compare Dimensions and CrossRef coverage to that of WoS, Scopus, Google Scholar, and Microsoft Academic. Cross-Ref and Dimensions had comparable or better coverage of publications and citation counts to WoS and Scopus but were significantly lower than Google Scholar and Microsoft Academic.

Bar-Ilan et al. (2012) GS has several features that can be attractive to educational researchers. Researchers create an "editable, verified (using an institutional email) profile including their details, a list of their papers, and citations to those papers".

Ortega (2015) notes that the appeal of GS lies in that it makes possible the definition of specific research units, mainly researchers, which can be compared with others inside the same institution or research interest. In addition, the comprehensive coverage of research materials in GS favours that these pages offer a wide view of the research production and impact. And finally, the fact that these profiles are publicly available helps that an author can be appreciated for a broader range of academic activities.

After reviewing some literature dealing with GS it can be summarized that GS is worldwide popular due

to its openness and easy-to-use user interface. Considering the popularity of GS this research was carried out.

Research Gap

Inferences are drawn from the review of literature that educators and researchers of different subjects utilize the features of GS worldwide. Superiority in features and unpaid access establish worldwide acceptance of GS. Nobel laureates also from the area of chemistry, physics, economics, and medicine have their profiles under the GS database. But in the case of literature laureates, the scenario is different. They have several documents under the GS database but those are not archived under individual GS profiles. This research will create and exhibits a sample GS profile of Tagore to prove its impressive presence with citations of writings under the GS database. To the best of my knowledge, there have been no prior studies that investigated the stability of Google Scholar coverage of Tagore's Literature. Thus this research chooses GS Database for making archives for Tagore's Literature. That archive also helps to exhibit the scientometrics data of Tagore.

Research Questions

The following questions will be answered after my study

- Q1. What is the GS Idof Rabindranath Tagore?
- Q2. What is the scenario GS profile of Tagore?
- Q3. What are the total citations of Tagore's Literature?
- Q4. What are the values of Indexes (h, g, I 10) of Tagore's GS profile?
- Q5. Which is the most cited work of Tagore on GS?
- Q6. How many times has the 'Nobel Work' been cited?
- Q7. What is the year-wise total citation?
- Q8. What is the duration of being cited?
- Q9. What is the ratio of citations per year?
- Q10. What is the ratio of authors per paper?

Objectives

- 1.To preserve and accumulate Tagore's literature under the author's profile by creating those profiles in the GS database.
- 2.To measure the current acceptance of Tagore's literature in respect of the GS document's total number, citations, h index, i10 index.
- 3.To rank the most prolific Nobel laureates in literature based on GS documents.
- 4.To identify the highest cited literature.
- 5.To showcase the citation of 'Nobel Work'.
- 6.To calculate year-wise total citation.

- 7.To compute the duration of being cited.
- 8.To prepare the ratio of citations per year.
- 9.To study the ratio of authors per paper.

Scope of the Study

The main focus of this research is archiving Tagore's literature under the GS database systematically. After completion of this process citation, the data will be collected and analyzed. The importance and acceptance of Tagore's literature in the current era also scrutinize during this study. This research accesses his literature's usefulness in modern literature by analyzing citations. Tagore's GS profile also will be available anytime from anywhere via the internet.

A limitation of this study is the dependency on GS ergo this study can only review those writings catalogued by the GS database whereas; GS sheltered most of the literature of Tagore. GS also enveloped Tagore's pieces of literature that are published in different languages however this study eliminated all those that were not published in English or Bengali language as Tagore's mostly writings are in these two languages. The early stage of Tagore's writing was the Bengali language biased as he belongs to the Bengali speaking community however later his writings are being translated into English.

Here in this study, Tagore's literature was considered because his literature carries the impression of the culture of that particular nation from where the author belongs. Literature has a strong connection with the culture so both are interlinked.

This research also qualifies the interest area of Digital Humanities (DH) by including both culture and literature. DH has multiple subfields but this topic comes under the subfields like Archiving & Data analytics. Another reason behind choosing this topic is the unavailability of a GS account of Tagore.

Research Methodology

Here for this research, a GS profile for Tagore's literature was created by following the under-mentioned steps in Figure1. During the process of GS profile creation, most articles were added one after another. As the GS profile holder is not alive so the profile update option is not useful for this scenario. To calculate accurate citations and indexes all those writings having the same name with multiple copies available under GS were merged. Duplicate and false entries were creating ambiguity in the scientometric data of Tagore therefore merging of duplicate copies and deletion of false entries solved this issue. Tagore's GS profile creation demanded continuous manual interference for getting

real data. Subsequently, Tagore's GS profile was analyzed by using different tools and methods.

Figure 1: Steps of the proposed research

Methodological Hurdles

It is not as easy as the research sounds. Every literature of Tagore demands careful review before adding under any GS profile. After reviewing various literature some hurdles were identified to be overcome, those are:

Unrealistic Data Range

This research will concentrate also on that laureate who does not alive so any new publication after the death of an author will be judged and verified carefully before adding under any GS profile. In this case, there is a chance of implausible data entry.

Multiple Dates

Some pieces of literature also have multiple publication dates which include the same title with different years of publication on this matter also have to take care of.

Literature without Author

Under GS various articles don't have their author name or not holding proper author names.

Duplicate Entry

Duplication of the record is another problem of this research. Under GS same article takes place multiple times. In this case, the same title will be identified and merged under a single title, or else the profile indexes (h, g, i10) show the wrong result.

Data Clinging

Under GS database various authors have the same name so have to choose the right author with the right publication is one of the crucial points.

Results & Discussion

Tagore's GS profile holds various attractive citation matrices. All data is sorted in table 1 with actual numeral values.

Serial No	Matrices	Value
1	Citation	6246
2	H-index	36
3	G-index	71
4	i-10 index	99
5	Author's Citation/Paper	12.45

Table-1: Prime findings of the research

This study also perceived two key drawbacks of GS during the making of Tagore's GS profile. GS has a pivotal drawback of not including more than 3000 thousand documents under a GS profile. More than 30 duplicate documents also can't be merged under a single original article.

Over 3000 documents can't be inlaid under any GS profile. Whereas after overcoming these hurdles Tagore's profile was made and from that profile data were collected and presented under table 1.

Figure-5: GS profile of Tagore

The GS profile of Rabindranath Tagore seems like old wine in a new cup that depicts all of the citation matrices. Figure5 is the screengrab of the author's profile with ID (giDssRQAAAAJ) denoted under the blue rectangle with a red arrow. Whereas Tagore's GS profile ID is not visible publicly under the GS database as the right to use this ID is restricted to the two authors of this article. This is the prime profile built by the authors of this research paper that profile played a key role in the study.

Figure-6: Top five cited Literature

Figure-7: Citation Metrics

Year-Wise Citations (1983-2021)

Figure-8: Citation counts (1983-2021)

Tagore's pieces of literature were mostly cited (514 times) in the year 2020. Further, in the years 2017(513 times), 2016 (453 times), 2018 (445 times), and 2015 (428 times) Tagore's works of literature were cited most of the time. In Figure8, the year-wise citation of Tagore's literature, from the year 1983 to 2021 was manifested. Based on Figure6, the top five cited pieces of literature are as follows in descending order Gitanjali, The Religion Man, Home and the World, Sadhana, and Creative Unity. However, the top most cited one is that masterpiece for which Tagore was being renowned all over the world by getting Nobel.

Scientometrics data of Tagore's literature undermined in figure6, figure7& figure8 adopted from GS unveils the popularity of Tagore's writings through the citation world. The faculties and research scholars who belong to the Literature field were not very visible under GS with their profiles, whereas the GS database indexed their articles. The unavailability of the GS profile of the writers who belong to the literature field can't portray the scientometric picture of those penmen. Therefore, it is necessary to amalgamate one's writings under a GS profile to evaluate the acceptance and quality of literature. Tagore's GS profile creation gives the impression that GS did not have biases towards the contents of science and social science. It also includes articles from the literature. Ergo GS provides an opportunity for all the authors as they can easily flourish in their profile.

Conclusion

The romantic & melancholy art exhibited in the novels of Rabindranath came from his empathy with the beauty and mystery in nature deeply rooted in social, family, and individual life. Reflection on changing social history was showcased in his novels. His short stories unveiled the problems relating to personal, familial, social, etc. These reflections can never be measured with mere scientometrics indicators. To realize the depth of Tagore's literature is implausible, however, by analyzing the scientometrical values this study was trying to gauge the popularity of the author's works of literature. The matrices of citation denote Tagore's pieces of literature have a huge impact & applicability in different fields. Qualitatively enriched literature builds huge followers who are passionate about Tagore's literature.

Various unpredictable hurdles and opportunities have appeared during the process but this research tried to overcome all the hurdles and welcomed all opportunities by which it can add more value. In the process of archiving under GS always manual verification of each entry was contemplated as data clinging and the data accuracy part could not be compromised. GS was released in 2004 but this research will archive and analyze those documents which are published before 2004 also. This research had the motive to draw the scientometrics portrait of Tagore.

While considering the scientometrics productivity of Rabindranath one should not forget that Rabindranath not only expressed his vision on society, education, rural development, and religion, through his numerous writings but he established his experimental school at Santiniketan and rural reconstruction program at Sriniketan. Ray, P., & Sen, B. (2015) narrated Tagore wished to "bring to the village health and knowledge, wealth and peace in which to live, wealth of time in which to work and to rest and enjoy". Not only was a writer he was famous but also he has a huge impact on social & educational reformation.

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